

Optimizing Indian Classical Music [ICM] to Cater to a Larger Listening Public and Generating a Sustainable Market

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Abstract

The practitioners of Indian Classical Music [ICM], India's intangible cultural heritage, are facing demand and supply imbalance. This imbalance has negatively impacted the musicians, and this rich and highly developed musical form is also facing a decline in its popularity index. The change of time, changes in the general pace of life, changes in the public value system, and changes in average sensitivity for classical arts are some of the major causes for these implications. This paper is based on the notions that (1) ICM can effectively serve a large volume of listening public, (2) Carefully curated ICM has the potential to satisfy general ICM-uninitiated listeners, and (3) this art form requires a larger market. The presentation is based on the investigator's long experience in ICM performances, academic orientation, and peripheral understanding of business principles through non-formal studies. The study tried to identify the causes, suggest methods to generate higher exchange values, and generate a sustainable market. The paper suggested taking up appropriate research to identify potential components and the optimized mix of music and allied components to cater to the challenges. The research outputs can be used for future applications in ICM for success in generating significantly higher exchange values from the large ICM-uninitiated listening public.

Keywords: Indian Classical Music, sustainable market, imbalance, exchange values, uninitiated listeners, optimization

The ICM connoisseurs are generally against taking ICM for general consumption, and the same was valid for puritan musicians. The connoisseurs wish to enjoy their exclusive status as listeners, and the musicians prefer to retain old values. The music was confined to the elitist group. ICM could make only negligibly few musicians' lives comfortable, and the rest had to accept dismal situations. As able presenters and practitioners of this rich heritage art, the musicians did not receive their due positions, respect, and remunerations. Bakhle, while amplifying her "yes, but" historical argument, stated the status of court musicians not as glorious as the authors portray while writing the successful history of classical music. The musicians were not seen as the exclusive torchbearers of the glorious music traditions. But opposite to it, they were treated as "specialized servants" to boost the image of the rulers in the then immaculately laid modernized courts. The state rulings did not even spare the ancient art music to put under the beam of the streamlining strategies (Bakhle, 2005, p. 257).

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During the last century, the musicians' questionable economic and societal positioning prompted the two giants, V.N. Bhatkhande (1860-1936) and V.D. Paluskar (1872-1931) to engage in thoughts. They put in their time and intense energy to improve the musicians' socio-economic status. They put in the best of their planned efforts to generate awareness and respect among the broader cross-section of society. They worked hard to inspire the educated middle-income group to understand, appreciate, and respect the values of ICM and successfully expanded the market. During the early twentieth century, musicians opted for travel distances to find markets. A group of people transitioning from middle to higher income groups in the port cities like Calcutta, Bombay and Madras took an interest to patronize music and support these musicians. These people started organizing public concerts and established music schools to serve interested people of the society (Roy, 2019). These efforts undoubtedly helped to stabilize the musicians' socio-economic crises partially. As a result, the musicians received better respect, opportunities, and employment through an extended market.

Does ICM require a larger market?

Comparing the early to mid-twentieth century, the second decade of the 21st century is experiencing a considerably changed situation. The current availability status of highly commendable musicians has increased significantly, but the demand did not grow enough to engage so many musicians. This situation needs a systematic review and analysis that can indicate methods for improving the situation.

After Ravi Shankar pitched in and successfully introduced ICM to the global market during the 1960s, that was a significant phase for disseminating ICM. Gradually, the lives of a larger chunk of musicians started becoming brighter. Also, the interested people started receiving better learning opportunities and broader scope to enjoy this rich art form with better distributions with the advancement of time and technology. With the change in time, corresponding changes in the general attitude of the musicians regarding teaching, and the availability of new facilities made it possible to make effective music pedagogy better available. As a result, the community received many able musicians. The general understanding among musicians was; music is a complex art, and if one can finally perform well, that will naturally lead to a broad presence in the music arena. The expected obvious result was automatic fame and wealth.

With the wider availability of effective music pedagogy and Ravi Shankar as a very bright musician with considerable money and fame, a larger population got involved with ICM and put in high efforts to master the art. As a result, the number of able ICM musicians become quite enormous and out of proportion to the demands.

The Challenges and Confusions of Able Musicians

The able musicians started facing stiffer challenges to run a comfortable life and get confused. The challenges occur because the established musicians try to retain their presence in the market and opt for different means that work, ethical and unethical. When the ability to perform impressively is the basic necessity to showcase in the market, the established musicians or their promoters put in considerable efforts to generate the market, retain it and enhance it. Most of the able musicians do not become established musicians because most of these people are unsuccessful in generating enough opportunities and present their art before the listening public as often as required to get established. Getting established also needs additional media support for required distribution and promotion.

Because the market is tiny, generally, established musicians try to defer new contestants' entries with the fear of loosening their footholds in the market. In Indian music parlance, the term 'politics' is commonly used. Here people use the word 'Politics' to express a musicians' actions as a tool to enhance or maintain their musician-status by degrading other musicians those they consider as threats (Clayton & Leante, 2015, p. 415). The striving musicians openly discuss that a musician must face politics and actively do politics to receive and retain due positioning in the ICM world.

Now, let us elucidate on the confusions of the new musicians. The musicians get confused because a big part of the able musician population [AMP] fails to meet their expectations of receiving enough opportunities to display their art. In most cases, the musicians receive highly compromised offers regarding fees payment, the required audio setup, and many other areas. This situation generated confusion among music practitioners. Some general confusions are:

- (a) the musicians may doubt their music performance competency
- (b) maybe unsure about the methods of receiving performance opportunities
- (c) uncertain about the ways of negotiations with the connected people or organizations
- (d) attributing the whole situation to one's fate or destiny

Money and ICM

The ICM world is running on an extremely low money-play. When the AMP is considerably high, the worldwide fund play is too small compared to even a single middle-sized profit-making standard company. As a result, the fund distribution is far from good and not proportionate considering the relative musical abilities of musicians.

The existing setup, resources, and operation style do not appear to work effectively to generate enough fund rolling to comfortably run the lives of able musicians. The able musicians here indicate the musicians capable of adequately impressing and enthralling their audiences, maintaining the general traditionality of ICM. The musicians frequently complain about disparities in fund distributions. Despite very low fund mobilization, a tiny population of musicians are well-paid. The reason for getting nicely-paid lies in the individual musicians' and their management supports' optimized actions in required areas, be it musical or music-allied. Here two points have come into discussion, one is musical, and the other is music-allied. A musician's optimized musical delivery indicates the created music that generates enough exchange values for audience participation. When the listeners participate silently or visibly with the music, the exchange values of music get generated. For musical success, audience participation is a crucial factor. Extra-musical or music-allied factors also play essential roles in developing exchange values other than the music itself. Some music-allied agents are audio transmission quality, visuals, and verbal communications. The delivered music must match the receptivity of the audience. Some prominent factors for audiences receptivity are the audiences' average (a) receptivity pace, (b) acceptable duration length, and (c) sensitivity to musical and visual impacts.

Remembering the Transitions and Survival of Cricket

Let us briefly shift our attention to cricket, how the demand for the game was going alarmingly down and how Kerry Packer successfully revived the demand status. During the 1970s, the test cricket was failing to draw enough spectators and, as Andrew Caro, a top gun of the World Series Cricket, pointed out, was gradually turning into a dead game. The Australian billionaire Kerry Packer stepped in; he played the key role in revolutionizing and rejuvenating cricket. Although Packer came under severe adverse comments from the puritans, cricket regained popularity. Later Kerry Packer was inducted by the MCC, an unquestionable recognition of his service to cricket (Kotter, 2009).

Some duly identified ICM experts can surely advise on how to frame ICM presentations for the wider public as Richie Benaud, the Australian Cricket Captain, recommended for cricket (Kotter, 2009). We can hope that the tweaked ICM recitals will win the hearts of a much larger listening public. A wider cross-section of ICM musicians will be better paid on broader market creation. This new market creation may also adjust the payment disparity to some degree.

Creating New Market

Any new market creation requires generating a new value curve. Present context pushes us to consider the ICM market from a contrastive angle with the popular music genres' market that has successfully developed a much larger market. One consideration may be maintaining similar lines on producing, distributing, and delivering the music. The other approach is putting the ICM market generation plan through RECR or Reduce, Eliminate, Create and Raise appropriately to create a compelling value curve.

1. Identify the existing music market factors that the ICM may reduce and remain attractive. | Reduceⁱ
2. Identification and elimination of factors that the thriving music market considers compulsory. | Eliminateⁱⁱ
3. Creation of elements that were never offered by the industry. | Createⁱⁱⁱ
4. Identify or generate factors and raise them above industry standards to create a unique attraction. | Raise^{iv}

This process will generate a new value curve (Kim & Mauborgne, 1999, p. 85). Once the concept of creating a new value curve is established, it will pave the way for a new market for ICM.

Seven Thought Influencers

1. Indian Classical Music [ICM] is a grand artistic practice.
2. ICM went through lots of changes with time.
3. ICM market is too low to cater to the population of able musicians.
4. The classicality of ICM is focused exclusively on audio components^v.
5. The disparity of fund distribution is common in all walks of life and art practices. Regulating disparities is very difficult. Market enlargement and improvement in fund flow should help in increased fund distributions among music practitioners.
6. ICM deserves a larger market.
7. Efforts for the enlargement of the ICM market is the call of the time.

Three Balancing Pillars

The three balancing pillars of this proposal are:

1. ICM components can be intelligently presented to impress the large public.
2. Carefully curated ICM has the potential to satisfy general ICM-uninitiated listeners.
3. A considerable population of ICM musicians possess the required virtuosity to present ICM recitals that can impress a wide cross-section of audiences with different listening tastes.

The Proposal

If the above three statements are true, then Optimized Indian Classical Music Presentations [OIP] can win the hearts of a wide cross-section of music lovers. We shall require optimizations maintaining the classicality of music. This optimization is an effort to establish smooth transmissions of the ideas, expressions, and finally generate appreciation from the listeners. OIP should help in establishing easy communications between the musician and audiences for mass participation and generate exchange values.

Optimized ICM Presentations [OIP]

One major quality for effective communication is to transmit symbols that the receivers can easily decode and enjoy. Optimization of ICM presentations is necessary to generate higher exchange values for a much larger listening public. One of the primary reasons for the failure of ICM is the types of musical applications that the larger mass cannot appreciate. When an assortment of the known and the unknown generates high interests, totally unknown symbols make things unintelligible.

In the case of music, the audiences must participate with the presented music and feel the exchange values.

OIP may include:

1. Duration optimization
2. Musical content distribution optimization
3. Audio transmission quality control
4. Visual component additions and optimizations^{vi}

It is vital to understand the effectivity index of applications of musical and its allied components. Some well-directed and systematic research can identify the riders for applications of music and music allied components that generate higher impact. It will be essential to retain the classicality of ICM and induct or subtract ingredients to generate higher impacts and higher exchange values.

Music Distribution and Profit Generation

- After successfully establishing the concepts, the presentations may be planned.
- The system may identify musicians and technicians.
- Readying of the items.
- Appropriate marketing and sales.

Preparations for content generation

The musical contents may be generated by:

- Musician identification
- Counselling the identified musicians for OIP.
- Quality monitoring of the developed contents.

Other important areas

- Assuring regular payments and additional payments for the registered musicians.
- Design a detailed plan to generate profit.
- Frame a detailed policy including rewards and demurrages.

Seed funding generation

- The company/organization may table a well-laid proposal assuring RoI or time-bound return of investments to the potential financiers, e.g. TATA group or try to obtain seed money from the financiers.
- If the group can generate business, then at the appropriate time, it can float some proposal proving its worth and promises and obtain money from the market for expansions^{vii}.

Project Setup

The first requirement is to construct a highly efficient core group that will design;

- (a) functioning methods
- (b) detailed policy for presentation generation, marketing, and sales.
- (c) Detailed policy for ongoing research to generate futuristic guides for updating the methods and executions in all functioning areas.

This core group should be formed with people possessing the following qualities:

- A. high cerebral capacity with high enthusiasm
- B. highly able Indian Classical Musicians
- C. preferably aged below 50 years.
- D. one member with expertise in Marketing with earlier stated qualities A, B, and C.
- E. One member should be an Expert in Sales who understands ICM and possesses the qualities stated in A and C above.

Challenges

The first challenge is to generate seed money. This part involves:

- A. Writing a project with:
 - a. SWOT analysis [Strength, Weakness, Opportunities and Threat analysis].
 - b. Establishing RoI or Return of Investment.
- B. Creating a presentation with supporting documents.
- C. Approaching the Funding Agencies, presenting the proposal, convincing them, and arranging the funding.

Homework before asking for funding

Here is a plan. It will be essential to run a Pilot Project, or some Pilot Shows to prove that there are good chances that the concept will work. The pilot project will be based on the musicians' ability to earn their performance time to help in their fees enhancements. This performance model requires testing if this can be a meaningful content creation step to generate a sustainable market for ICM by creating considerable exchange values. There may be several shows, say five shows. During the presentations, the managers must obtain research data by getting responses from the audiences and the complete video recording of the audiences during a concert. All the accumulated data should be duly processed to generate results proving the generation level of exchange values and thereby ascertain the potentials of the performance and delivery strategies.

Musicians' Play in Creating a Sustainable Indian Classical Music [ICM] Market

Any service and its corresponding market status rest on two primary factors, (a) the level and quality of the service generated exchange values and (b) optimized distribution of the service among the prospective users or buyers. The present discussion is on an ICM content delivery method to establish the music's competency to be a market-compliant service. This design is focused on the music presentations to generate excellent exchange values from the audiences.

In this model, the musicians require to earn their performance time by generating exchange values. Here is an example of how it may build up. The methods will get optimized from the findings of the value generation audit.

A suggested model

1. A musician team may receive the first 7 minutes to generate audience exchange values by rendering an awe-inspiring performance.
 - a. If the musician team fails to generate the exchange values, the team receives the negotiated minimum payment and leaves the stage for the next musician.
 - b. If the musician team successfully generates the exchange values, the team gets 20% additional payment over the negotiated minimum fees and receives 10 minutes for the second rendering.
2. With this 10 minutes second item:
 - a. If the musician team fails to generate the exchange values, the team receives the 20% enhanced payment and leaves the stage for the next musician.
 - b. If the musician-team successfully generates the exchange values, they get 30% additional payment over the negotiated minimum fees and receives 20 minutes for subsequent rendering.
3. With this 20 minutes third item:
 - a. If the musician team fails to generate the exchange values, the team receives the 50% enhanced payment and leaves the stage for the next musician.
 - b. If the musician-team successfully generates the exchange values, the team gets 50% additional payment over the negotiated minimum fees and receives another 30 minutes of performance time.
4. With this 30 minutes third item:
 - a. If the musician team fails to generate the exchange values, the team receives the 100% enhanced payment and leaves the stage for the next musician.
 - b. If the musician team successfully generates such exchange values from the audience like shouts for 'more ... more' and don't stop clapping, the musician gets 100% additional payment over the negotiated minimum fees and perform longer to satisfy the audiences and limits the final item to 60 minutes.

- After the completion of the 97 minutes performance, the musician team may receive three times the negotiated minimum payable fees.

Stage	Description	Pay condition [INR]	Payable [INR]
Stage 1	A music team booked at a minimum payable. Stage time 7 minutes	10,000	10,000
Stage 2	Additional stage time 10 mins. and add the bonus to pay 120% of basic as final payment	2,000	12,000
Stage 3	Additional stage time 20 mins. and add the bonus to pay 130% of basic as final payment	3,000	15,000
Stage 4	Additional stage time 30 mins. and add the bonus to pay 150% of basic as final payment	5,000	20,000
Stage 5	Additional stage time 60 mins. and add the bonus to pay 300% of basic as final payment	10,000	30,000
Limits	97 minutes	-	30,000

The "earn your time and bonus" is expected to be a welcome game for any able musician team. Here all musicians will receive the minimum fees even the group fails to generate the desired level of exchange values. However, a successful musician team will receive three times or 300% payment of the base fees. This model will help to generate high exchange values, a healthy challenge to the musicians and, as a result, develop a sustainable and more extensive market for ICM. All the data generated from the pilot project, follow up events, and their systematic analysis will show ways for future strategy planning to improve results.

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Notes:

ⁱ ICM may reduce the visual elements in music. Visuals play a significant role in popular music. But, in ICM, visual elements are kind of neglected. As opposed to visuals, the central focus here is audio. However, ICM renderings may creatively consider the scope for using visuals to enhance exchange values for wider listening public without significant deviations from its central audio focus.

ⁱⁱ Eliminate dance and explicit body movements. ICM does not include dance and explicit body movements during its vocal and instrumental music recitals, so ICM can easily exclude these common components of popular music genres.

ⁱⁱⁱ For creation of elements that were never offered by the industry, I wonder if the ICM presenters may consider collaborating with other art forms, e.g. magic, as a tool to generate higher exchange values among the larger listening public. It can also consider using third sensory values experimentally, e.g. smell or Fragrance. The musicians may creatively consider relating Fragrance with the mood of the music.

^{iv} ICM productions may raise Focus on audio elements. Here are some points occurred to me:

- The ICM recitals should appropriately emphasize the universal audio components of music for wider audience involvement. Creators should do it along with the culture-specific elements to retain classicality. Appropriate applications of universal audio components will help to enhance the exchange values.
- ICM recitals should never compromise with the high-quality audio transmission.
- ICM may experiment using new audio transmission methods to advantage, e.g. 5-point surround sound.
- ICM recitals may engage proficient audio-distribution managers during live concerts.

^v If we look at the musical treatises, we can see that all are focused on descriptions and analysis of audio and very little on the visuals. Some brief discussion on visuals occurred in '*gAyak vAdako ke gun doS*'. The intention for bringing visuals of music in the discourse is to argue that if ICM freshly adapts visual elements in its delivery, this will not violate the dictums of the treatises. The obvious reason is the detailed discussion on visuals are absent in the treatises. So, any new focus on visual elements or even new applications of fresh audio transmissions ideas is not a deviation from classicality. If new changes happen and succeed in increasing the exchange values of ICM to the broader public and help to create a more extensive market, this will be good news. It is good to mention that during earlier times, the audio formats considerably changed with time, from *prabandh* to *dhrupad* to *khayAl* and still accepted as classical.

^{vi} Ravi Shankar at one point tried simple Visual Applications but did not continue.

^{vii} Generating money from the market by floating market shares may appear too ambitious at this point of time. But, there is no harm in dreaming big or bluntly consider ICM as a future mini-industry.